

Declaratio Regis.

Referring to my enactment of 25.11.2019 {1} I declare the Vatican City State to be illegal, nullify its state sovereignty and independence from Italy, and initiate the criminal proceedings against officials of the catholic church and in justified cases against abettors for reasons that have been explained previously.

The annulment of Vatican concerns also the Holy See, the catholic church as a whole, and other, not mentioned here governmental and administrative offices, agencies, and institutions, created by or under the authority of the Vatican, the Holy See or the catholic church.

As from now, the Vatican City is a part of Italy, that implies the revocation of all interstate and intergovernmental agreements and covenants, the removal of the article 7 from the Constitution of the Italian Republic or its complete recast due to invalidity of the Lateran Treaty, and the refund of payments received by Vatican and its officials, representatives or citizens from Germany.

To cover all expenditures of the criminal proceedings, to ensure the refund of payments from Germany, and to compensate indemnitees, I order the seizure of ecclesiastic assets and property for declared purposes.

The government and officials of Italy and other states are obligated to cooperate in this administrative and criminal case.

Dr. Andrej Poleev
Berlin, 1.01.2020.

Reference.

1. Enactment of 25.11.2019.

<http://constitution.fund/letters/Zerschlagung.pdf>